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The Socioeconomic Effects Of Current War On Rural Household Livelihood In Algoze Locality, South Kordofan State, Sudan

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ABSTRACT

The current Study was conducted in Algoze locality in South Kordofan state during the year 2024. The Study was a comparative study concerning socioeconomic variables of residents' households before and during the current war. The primary data were collected through field survey via structured questionnaire distributed to 138 households selected randomly. The study used descriptive statistics and (T) test correlation coefficient as well as Household Economy Approach (HEA). The results showed that percentage of respondents gender 88.5% were male, 50.4% of respondents were farmers, 21.6% were workers and 28% were merchants, 94.2% were married, 87.8% have children in education age, 84.9% have children in school, the reasons' for children left school, 74.1% left school for war and insecurity causes. 96.4% of the respondents said that the war has affected education. Medication cost increased during war reaching increment of 220%. Average monthly household income increased by 30% during war. Average household revenue during war increased by 40%, the average amount of non-wood products collected before war was more than average that collected during war. Average amount of wood products collected before war were more than collected during war. The average income from wood products collected by household before war was more than average income from wood products collected by household during war. The average household crop production from mechanized cultivated area before war was more than average household crop production from mechanized area during war. The average household crop production income from mechanized cultivated area before war was less than the income during war. Inflation rate in study area (220%) was more than the general inflation rate of the Sudan (193.7%). Study concluded that the war has affected respondent's income, expenditure, livestock and crop production wood products and hence affect food security situation. Strategies and new technologies were recommended as solutions to mitigate effects of war in study area.

Keywords: War, Socioeconomic Effects, Household Economy Approach, South kordofan State

INTRODUCTION

Civil conflict remains important in many developing countries and has become an integral part of the study of economic development. Especially the last decade has seen a boom in studies on conflict. (Blattman and Miguel (2010) One finding that stands out from this work is the strong negative association between conflict and economic development. However, while conflict may lead to poor economic performance, the reverse relationship seems equally credible, and this complicates the analysis. (Djankov and Reynal-Querol (2010) very little known about the micro-economic mechanisms underlying post-war recovery (or lack thereof). Shemyanika (2011) presents evidence of

the negative impact of conflict on schooling in the case of Tajikistan marry either earlier or later, and had children earlier.

Chamarbagwala and Morán (2011) find a strong negative effect of the war in Guatemala on the education of Mayan men and women in rural areas, the most disadvantaged groups. In contrast, Arcand and Wouabe (2009), find that conflict increased school enrolment in Angola.

Walque (2004), who observes that fertility and marriage rates in Cambodia were very low under the Khmer Rouge but bounced back after the regime collapsed

Civil war has been both prevalent and increasingly persistent during the past sixty years and yet, until relatively recently, had received little attention from economists (Fearon, 2004). Blattman and Miguel (2010) estimates that since 1960, twenty percent of all countries have experienced at least ten years of civil conflict and, given the important role civil conflict plays in shaping nations, it ought to be central to the study of economic development.

Internal conflicts are a constant threat to economic development worldwide. Over half of the nations have experienced an armed conflict at some point in the last 50 years (Pettersen and Wallenstein 2015). After a drop at the end of the 20th century, there has been an upward trend in the number of internal conflicts since the early 2000s. The Uppsala Conflict Data Program (UCDP) globally recorded 40-armed conflicts with at least 25 battle deaths per annum for 2014, the highest number on record after 1999. Over 25% of these conflicts were civil wars that caused more than 1,000 battle deaths in a single year. The data also show that in 2014 the number of people forcibly displaced by armed conflicts worldwide reached close to 60 million, making it the highest annual increase since comparable records began in 1989 (United Nations High Commission for Refugees 2014).

Civil conflicts are a source of huge devastation, ranging from loss of lives and forced displacement, destruction of human capital, physical infrastructure and private property to disruption of economic and political systems. Internal warfare has spillover effects in the form of refugees, crime and illegal trade into neighboring nations. At the macro level, countries often see growth slowdown shortly after armed conflicts surge. Over time, however, most countries experience rapid post-war economic recovery, including convergence of key factors of production (population and human capital) and standards of living (Blattman and Miguel 2010; Miguel and Roland 2006; Brakman et al. 2004; Davis and Weinstein 2002). Yet, at the micro level, a growing body of empirical research has been uncovering how wars inflict a subtler but long-lasting burden on the human capital of affected populations, undermining their long-term productivity and wellbeing (Bundervoet et al. 2009; Akbulut- Yuksel, 2017; Akresh et al. 2011).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data resources, primary data were collected via questionnaire to interview selected households, secondary data were collected from similar previous studies and relevant researches, sampling and sample size: multi stage random sampling technique was used. Descriptive statistics, Correlation analysis, T test and Household Approach (HEA) were used for food security analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table (1) described the status of children in school, 2.9% were having children in school, and 84.9% were they have no children in school.

Table (1) Respondents who have children in school now, for education variable

Statement	Frequent	Percentage
Yes	4	2.9
No	181	84.9
total	122	87.8

Source: Filed survey 2024

Table (2) explains the reasons' for children left school 74.1% left school for war and insecurity causes.

Table (2) Respondents' reasons for why children left school.

Statement	Frequent	Percentage
Not interested	4	2.9
Expensive	4	2.9
Marginal work	1	0.7
Farm work	4	2.9
Herding	1	0.7
Move to town	1	0.7
War cause	103	74.1
total	118	84.9

Source Filed survey 2024

Table (3) showed the respondents answers about private school fees, 81.3% answers the fees of private education was high,15.8% answer the fees of private education were moderate,2.9% answers they have no children learning in private school.

Table (3) showed that 96.4% respondents answers that education operation was affected by war, 3.6% said education operation was not affected by war.

Table (3) the respondents' perceptions about whether the education was affected by the war

Statement	Frequent	Percentage
Yes	134	96.4
No	5	3.6
total	139	100

Source: Filed survey 2024

Table (4) reveal type of war effects in education, 59.0% said war effects education institutions, and 37.4% answer war affected the human recourses

Table (4) the respondents' perception about type of war effects on education operation

Statement	Frequent	Percentage
Institutional effects	82	59.0
Human effects	52	37.4
Total	139	96.4

Source: Filed survey 2024

Table (5) showed the respondents perception about existence of health services in study area, 70.5% mention there was health services in study area, and 29.5% deny the existence of health services in their area.

Table (5) the respondents' perceptions about the existence of health services

Statement	Frequent	Percentage
Yes	98	70.5
No	41	29.5
total	139	100

Source Filed survey, 2024

Table (6) showed the respondents perceptions about availability of health services in the study area before war, 95% answer they has health services

Table (6) the respondents' perceptions about the availability of health services before war

Statement	Frequent	Percentage
Available	132	95
Not available	7	5
total	139	100

Source: Filed survey 2024

Table (7) revealed the respondents perceptions about sources of income, 57.6% were farmers, 25.9% were merchants.

Table (7) Respondents perceptions about main family income sources

Sources of income	Frequent	Percentage
Farmer	80	57.6
Merchant	36	25.9
Herding	1	0.7
Labor	2	1.4
Remittance gifts , charities	8	5.8
More than one source	11	8.6
Total	138	100

Source: Filed survey 2024

Table (8) showed significant difference between cost of medication before war, and during war, (T) test the probability value of (T) test equal (15.471), which is less than the significant level value (0.000) therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, mean there is rising of medication cost during war in the study area ..

Table (8) T test results for the independent tow samples for cost of medication correlation

T test	Degree of freedom	Sample size	averages		Sig value
			before	during	
15.471	137	138	104,833.33	338,405.80	0.000

SPSS.V23 analysis output, 2024

Table (9) show significant difference between the average monthly household income, before war and during war, (T) Test probability value equal (- 3.426), less than the significant value level (0.001), therefore we reject the null-hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis at (0.05), we concluded that the average monthly household income before war was less than average monthly household income during war.

Table (9) T test for the independent twos samples correlation and difference between the two averages of monthly income before and during war.

T test	Degree of freedom	Sample size	averages		Sig value
			before	during	
-4.263	133	134	120246.27	160579.10	0.001

SPSS.V23 analysis output 2024

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Study concluded that war has effects on the rural household socioeconomics and livelihood in study area, There was rising cost of social services (education, health care, and social expenditure during war in study area, education operation was affected by war and insecurity, average monthly household income during war was more than before war, even within the deterioration of production and livelihood systems.

Recommendations;

- National reform and re- construction program, justices and equity concepts, and restore social enclosure bases.
- Comprehensive economic development strategies, footing stone for peace and sustainable development

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